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A new linear programming Jlp22 algorithm for forest-level planning problems including factories

Juha Lappi

Norwegian University of Life Sciences

juha.lappi.sjk@gmail.com

Highlights:

- Formulation for linear programming planning problems including factories and second level factories;
- Efficient algorithm using the generalized upper bound technique to get rid of three types of area constraints saying that proportions add up properly;
- In each optimization step optimal factories and the optimal schedule are chosen simultaneously;
- Implementation in Jlp22 software or elsewhere is discussed.

Abstract

Such forest planning approach is analyzed where simulator first generates for each stand treatment schedules describing timber harvests in different periods, and linear programming is used to maximize forest-wide objective under forest-wide constraints. Linear programming formulation has for each stand so-called area constraint requiring that proportions treated in a stand with different treatments add up to the one. Area constraints have been efficiently treated with the generalized upper bound technique. A linear programming formulation in which transportation of timber to factories and transportation of part of timber to second level factories is presented. Typically, first level factory is sawmill, and second level factory pulp mill receiving chips from sawmills. There are two additional area constraints for each stand in this formulation. A method is derived which combines all three area constraints into one area constraint which can be treated using the generalized upper bound technique. In the method each schedule is extended into several extended schedules which tell for

each timber type first level factory and linked second level factory. One optimization step selects simultaneously optimal schedule and optimal factories and linked factories for all timber types. The algorithm is intended to be used in Jlp22 software, but it can be used also elsewhere. Requirements for the simulator and optimization software are discussed. The algorithm is simpler and evidently more efficient than the previous algorithm of J software which iterated between optimization of schedules and factories of each timber type separately. Theoretically the algorithm belongs to decomposition methods of linear programming.

Keywords: Generalized upper bound technique; Decomposition in linear programming; Software development; Transportation costs; Forest simulator

1 Introduction

Lappi (1992) developed an algorithm and software for traditional linear programming problems in forestry where a simulator first simulates for each stand treatment schedules for different periods and linear programming (LP) is used to combine schedules so that a forest-wide objective is maximized under a set of forest-wide constraints. The objective and constraints are expressed as linear combinations of variables generated by the simulator for each stand. The variables describe typically amounts of harvested wood and costs of treatments. Typical constraints require even or non-decreasing flow of timber for next 50 years. The algorithm and the software were called JLP. Such problems include so called area constraints, which tell that areas treated according to different schedules add up to the total area of the stand or proportions of schedules add up to one (as assumed here). The solution time of LP problems depends on the number of constraints. If there are thousands of stands, the area constraints made standard LP algorithms slow or prevented solution.

JLP algorithm removes area constraint utilizing the generalized upper bound (GUB) technique of Dantzig and van Slyke (1967). JLP has been used in the Finnish MELA planning system since 1991. Hirvelä et al (2017) is the most recent reference to MELA. In 2004 I published a new software J as a successor for JLP. J used matrix subroutines of Fletcher based on Fletcher (1996), as JLP used my own matrix subroutines. In addition to linear programming, J contained many tools for data analysis, matrix computations and graphics. Initially J could not handle factories. MELA has been used to compute long term national scenarios which may not be realistic as they have not considered factories. Forest planning problems with factories analyze simultaneously the harvesting of timber in specific stands and the transportation of logs to factories and transportation of secondary products from first level

factories to second level factories, e.g. transportation of chips from sawmills to pulp mills or power plants and transportation of bark from sawmills and pulp mills to power plants. With Reetta Lempinen we made a version of J which could handle also first level factories (Lappi and Lempinen 2014). The algorithm is complicated and slow. The second level factories were not explicitly considered which leads to inefficient solution where chips at sawmills must be treated defining new linear programming decision variables. Factory optimization of J was used in Hyvönen et al (2019).

Institute of Natural Resources (Luke) decided in 2017 to publish J as open-source software, as I had suggested in 2015 while working for Luke. Luke did not publish J and Luke did not allow me to publish it and rejected any co-operation in publication until I got in October 2021 permission to publish and develop the software. In 2022 I published a new, completely rewritten version of J. The new software was named Jlp22, partly to avoid confusion with the programming language J, partly to indicate that it is totally different from J. Jlp22 is available as open-source software at github.com/juhalappi/jlp22. New versions are updated irregularly, and versions are identified by the publication date. Jlp22 package has tools for convenient generation of Latex code for new manual versions and for generating a script file for all examples of the manual.

JLP, J and Jlp22 have been used in the Norwegian GAYA planning system. For recent developments see Strimbu et al. (2023). J has been also used in Simo software (Rasinmäki et al 2019). The developers of the software now working in Awry are still using J in their planning software, even if their documentation does not contain any reference to J.

JLP was written in Fortran 77, J in Fortran 90 and Jlp22 is using Gfortran implementing Fortran 2018 which is close to Fortran 90. JLP, J and Jlp22 are used using script-based interfaces. Users of JLP, J or Jlp22 need not know Fortran. The script language of Jlp22 provides a powerful programming environment.

Jlp22 includes a cleaned version of the dirty linear programming algorithm of J but without factories. In March 2024, I discovered how factory optimization can be done in much simpler and more efficient way. I started to implement the algorithm, but other tasks intervened. I decided to publish the mathematics of the algorithm first as it anyhow needs to be published outside the continuously changing manual. The algorithm can be implemented also outside Jlp22. I cannot see any reason why it would be implemented in software not using the GUB technique to treat area constraints. I call the new algorithm Jlp22 algorithm, even if the factories are not yet implemented. Writing this report will help with the implementation.

The heuristic DTRAN algorithm of Hoganson & Kapple (1991) based on Hoganson and Rose (1984) has been able to treat factories from the beginning. DTRAN updates shadow prices with a heuristic algorithm until the mathematical conditions for an LP solution are satisfied closely enough. The iterations of JLP, J and Jlp22 without factories are similar to DTRAN algorithm. JLP, J and Jlp22 update shadow prices using standard LP matrix theory. DTRAN produces integer solutions, i.e., it does not split stands to different treatment schedules. JLP, J and Jlp22 split some stands to meet constraints precisely. The suggested Jlp22 algorithm selects factories in a similar, simple way as DTRAN. The simplicity of DTRAN assured me that there must be simpler solutions to factory problems than found in Lappi and Lempinen (2014).

Here a basic knowledge of linear programming is assumed or can be obtained e.g. from Luenberger and Ye (2008). The proposed algorithm is a revised simplex algorithm which solves iteratively linear equations $\mathbf{Ax} = \mathbf{b}$ with $\mathbf{x} \geq \mathbf{0}$ trying to maximize $\mathbf{c}'\mathbf{x}$. Variables in \mathbf{x} are the decision variables of the LP problem. \mathbf{A} has usually far more columns than rows (constraints). Let T be the number of rows. In each phase there is a $T \times T$ matrix \mathbf{A}_b consisting of columns of \mathbf{A} and vector $\mathbf{x}_b \geq \mathbf{0}$ so that $\mathbf{A}_b\mathbf{x}_b = \mathbf{b}$. \mathbf{A}_b is the basis matrix and variables in \mathbf{x}_b are basic variables. Local improvement is done by entering one column into the basis and leaving one column out so that constraints remain satisfied and $\mathbf{c}'\mathbf{x}$ increases. Entering columns are chosen using prices v_i for each row. The prices are computed with standard matrix algebra. The columns of \mathbf{A} need not exist before, they can be computed in flow as needed.

The new algorithm is evidently much more efficient than the algorithm of Lappi and Lempinen (2014). It's also much simpler. Over many decades, a huge number of linear programming algorithms have been published for several special cases. The algorithm is a decomposition algorithm whose principles were published already in Hillier and Lieberman (1973). Even if the algorithm does not provide anything theoretically new, it may provide a practical well-defined efficient solution for typical forest planning problems with factories.

The paper has three objectives:

1. To describe linear programming factory optimization formulations considering both transportation of timber to first level factories, e.g. sawmills, and transportation from first level factories to second level factories, e.g. chips from sawmills to pulp mills. The problem formulation in Lappi and Lempinen (2014) for the first level factories is not quite adequate.

2. To develop an efficient linear programming algorithm specially designed for the factory optimization problems and describe it in general mathematical terms so that it can be directly implemented in Jlp22 software or elsewhere.
3. To discuss implementation of the algorithm in Jlp22 or in other software and requirements for a simulator to produce proper data for factory problems.

A reader without background knowledge in linear programming may concentrate on the general description of planning problems with factories and software perspectives. Scientifically, the proposed algorithm is the main thing.

2 Linear programming forestry problems without factories

LP problems treated here need to be described in two different ways. Users of the software need an easily understandable form used in the software interface. Programmers need a description they can use in computations. There are two types of variables needed in the forestry problems considered here. Variables obtained from the forest are called x variables. Harvested pine saw log volume in period 3 is a typical x variable. Variables which are not x variables and cannot be computed from x variables are z variables. A typical z variable is a slack variable in goal programming which tells how much the total harvested pine saw log volume in period 3 is smaller than the target.

It is assumed that there are m stands and for stand i there are $n(i)$ simulated schedules. Simulated value of k 'th x variable in stand i and schedule j is denoted as x_k^{ij} . Note that x_k^{ij} is a constant generated with the simulator. Let w_{ij} be the proportion of the area of stand i treated with schedule j ; w_{ij} variables are LP decision variables. Let $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_k, \dots, x_p)$ denote total amounts in the whole forest. Problems both in JLP, J and Jlp22 without factories can be expressed

$$\text{Max } h_0 \tag{1}$$

subject to

$$L_t \leq h_t \leq U_t, t = 1, \dots, T \tag{2}$$

In (1) and (2) $h_t, t = 0, \dots, T$ is

$$h_t == \sum_{k=1}^q b_{tk} z_k + \sum_{k=1}^p \alpha_{tk} x_k \quad (3)$$

In Eq. (3)

$$x_k == \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^{n(i)} x_k^{ij} w_{ij}, \quad k = 1, \dots, p \quad (4)$$

Sign ‘==’ means that the right side is substituted to the symbol on the left side in computations.

Defining problems in terms of aggregate x_k variables is intuitive for users. I have called constraints in this form ‘utility constraints’. The matrix algebra of linear programming is based on equalities. If there are constraints so that $L_t < U_t$, so called slack and surplus variables, or residual variables, are used to express inequalities as equalities.

To solve the problem, it needs to be written in a different form. After writing (4) into (3) and after changing the order of summations, we get:

$$h_t == \sum_{k=1}^q b_{tk} z_k + \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^{n(i)} \left(\sum_{k=1}^p \alpha_{tk} x_k^{ij} \right) w_{ij} \quad (5)$$

Eq. (5) is the traditional way to translate a user defined problem Eq. (3) to solvable LP problem where variables w_{ij} are the linear programming decision variables. JLP, J and Jlp22 have computed $\sum_k \alpha_{tk} x_k^{ij}$ in (5) before optimization as a new x_k variable with coefficient one. This efficient solution, which I have called one- x formulation, is not of interest in factory problems.

An LP problem with x_k variables needs an area constraint for each stand i :

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n(i)} w_{ij} = 1 \quad (6)$$

The area constraint says that each part of the stand is treated with one schedule. When developing the JLP software, I noticed how one can get rid of area constraints with arithmetic manipulation. The solution was finally so evident that I was certain that it had been invented earlier. Indeed, Danzig and Van Slyke (1967) had published it and called the method generalized upper bound (GUB) technique.

The key point in GUB is to express a basic (usually nonzero) w_{ij} in the current solution in terms of the other w_{ij} variables. That schedule j in stand i is called the key schedule. The area constraints are automatically satisfied after moving constant terms to the right side and expressing schedules as difference between a schedule and the current key schedule. Key schedules can change all the time. A description of the GUB technique is in Lappi (1992). In addition to the GUB technique for area constraints, JLP, J and Jlp22 have used the ordinary upper bound technique with which a constraint having different lower bound L_t than upper bound U_t can be treated as a single constraint which at each phase of the optimization keeps either L_t or U_t active.

3 Factories

3.1 Factory problems

In planning problems including factories we need to consider

- How different tree assortments, such as saw logs and pulp logs are transported from each stand into different factories in different periods.
- How chips and bark produced in sawmills is transported to power plants or pulp factories.

There are usually two types of factory rows in LP problem definitions:

- Utility rows which tell the value of transported timber after subtracting transportations costs. Typically, the objective row h_0 is the only utility row.
- Capacity rows dealing with factory capacities. Capacities are usually present in constraints.

Lappi and Lempinen (2014) described factory problems using variables x_{ikf} which are the amounts of x_k transported from stand i to factory f . It was assumed that in each stand the total amount of transported x_k is equal to the amount of produced x_k :

$$\sum_{f=1}^F x_{ikf} = \sum_{j=1}^{n(i)} x_k^{ij} w_{ij} \quad (7)$$

This assumption was based on the naïve assumption that simulated sawlog and pulp log volumes are equal to sawlog and pulp log volumes bucked. I showed in Lappi (2024) that when the current dominant Finnish assortment pricing is used, the profit maximization requires companies owning both sawmills and pulp mills to buck smaller sawlog volumes than independent sawmills. It is generally known that this happens also in practice, even if research cannot confirm this as researchers cannot access the relevant data. In addition to x_{ikf} variables, the formulation of Lappi and Lempinen (2014) included y_{kfg} variables which were used to describe the utilities (including transportation costs) of x_{ikf} . The relation between x_{ikf} and y_{kfg} was again based assumption that simulated log volumes are equal to log volumes transported.

Here LP problems with factories are described with rows

$$h_t = \sum_{k=1}^q b_{tk} z_k + \sum_{k=1}^p \alpha_{ijk} x_k + \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^{n(i)} \sum_{k=1}^p \sum_{f=1}^F (\lambda_{ijkf} x_k^{ij}) w_{ijkf} + \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^{n(i)} \sum_{k=1}^p \sum_{f=1}^F \sum_{g=1}^F (\gamma_{ijkfg} x_k^{ij}) w_{ijkfg} \quad (8)$$

where w_{ijkf} is the share of area in stand i and schedule j from where x_k is transported to factory f , and w_{ijkfg} is the share of area used for transporting x_k in stand i and schedule j first to factory f and transported thereafter to factory g . Summation over schedule index j is second to emphasize that in stands we combine schedules. In fact, in most stands, only one schedule is needed. Row h_0 is maximized, other rows can have lower limit L_t or upper limit U_t , or both.

When comparing Eq. (8) to Eq. (5) we note first that in (5) α depends only on row t and variable k while in (8) α depends, or may depend also on stand i and schedule j . This generalization allows us to make modifications to simulated x_k^{ij} values in the optimization phase. It may not be needed in first applications, but as it does not cause any trouble, it is easier to make it now than add it later when needed.

Coefficients λ_{ijkf} in (8) can typically expressed as :

$$\lambda_{ijkf} = s_{ikf} \lambda_{ijkf}^* \quad (9)$$

where s_{ikf} tells the share of transported x_k from the simulated x_k^{ij} values. Coefficient s_{ikf} can consider that the actual sawlog percentage for independent sawmills and sawmills owned by pulp companies may be different and that sawlog percentage can be smaller for stand i owned by people living in a city and not being able to control or punish poor bucking. In utility rows λ_{ijkf}^* is the net utility of transported x_k considering also the transportation cost. In capacity rows λ_{ijkf}^* may be one, perhaps with species-dependent modifier. Coefficient s_{ikf} for pulp wood logs needs to be in synchrony with s_{ikf} of sawlogs. With s_{ikf} we can consider that part of volume may be forgotten in forest or stolen during the transportation. Note that bucked sawlogs can become pulp wood also by transporting sawlogs directly to pulp mills.

Coefficient γ_{ijkfg} may be presented as:

$$\gamma_{ijkfg} = s_{kif} r_{kfg} \gamma_{ijkfg}^* \quad (10)$$

where s_{kif} is the share of x_k transported to f , r_{kfg} is the share of x_k transported to factory f which is further transported to g . Coefficient γ_{ijkfg}^* can then be related to the net utility or come from the capacity constraints. If simulated x_k^{ij} values have biases which are not related to f , g or i , they can be corrected before feeding data to optimization.

It may help with the initial understanding of the factory problems to think that w_{ijkf} is the share of transported x_k , i.e., to assume that $s_{ikf} = 1$. But to help keep the distinction between ‘true’ and simulated values in mind, I’ll assign areas w_{ijkf} to factories which allows the correction of simulated values with s_{ikf} . Subindex j is added into α , λ and γ to allow more generality, even if in first applications of Eq. (8), λ and γ probably do not depend on j

We have now three generalized area constraints. For each i, j, k and f the areas from which x_k is transported first to factory f and thereafter to factories g add to the total area where x_k from schedule j is transported first to factory f :

$$\sum_g w_{ijkfg} = w_{ijkf} \quad (11)$$

The formulation of Lappi and Lempinen (2014) based on the idea of transported volume to factories may produce rather reasonable results with respect to sawlogs transported to sawmills. But I cannot see how transporting chips from sawmills to pulp mills could be formulated without collecting first sawlogs into sawmills and then distributing part of them further to pulp mills. This would cause an additional hierarchical level into the optimization with new LP decision variables which can be avoided treating weights w_{ijkfg} as proportion of the total area of the stand.

For each i, j and k , the areas from which x_k is transported to different factories add to the total area where schedule j is applied:

$$\sum_f w_{ijkf} = w_{ij} \quad (12)$$

Eq. (7) shows that Lappi and Lempinen (2014) collected all x_k coming from different schedules together and distributed the total amount in a stand to factories. I claim that a more efficient and simpler algorithm is obtained assigning w_{ij} of each schedule to different factories.

The areas of schedules add up to the total area:

$$\sum_j w_{ij} = 1 \quad (13)$$

Thus, in factory problems with two levels of factories, we have three area constraints instead of one in ordinary planning problems.

3.2 Defining factory problems with extended schedules

Factory problems can be described in a better way than with Eqs. (8)-(13) using extended schedules defined as:

$$\mathbf{x}^{ij+} = (\mathbf{x}^{ij}; \mathbf{f}^{j+}, \mathbf{g}^{j+}) = (x_1^{ij}, \dots, x_k^{ij}, \dots, x_p^{ij}; f_1^{j+}, \dots, f_k^{j+}, \dots, f_p^{j+}; g_1^{j+}, \dots, g_k^{j+}, \dots, g_p^{j+}) \quad (14)$$

Vector \mathbf{x}^{ij} tells the simulated amounts of x_k variables in schedule j in stand i . Extended schedule index j^+ indicates that the extended schedule is based on the simulated schedule j . The upper limit of j^+ is not written explicitly as we don't need to enumerate the extended schedules during the optimization. Factory f_k^{j+} is a factory to which x_k^{ij} variable is assigned. When considering transportation of chips from sawmills to pulp mills, we need also a linked factory g_k^{j+} to which a proportion of the area for x_k^{ij} assigned to f_k^{j+} is assigned. If f_k^{j+} and g_k^{j+} are in subindexes, they are written in form $f_k(j^+)$ and $g_k(j^+)$. It is described later, how it is easy to extend an extended schedule in (14) by allowing sister factories to g factories. If chips from sawlogs are transported into g factories, the bark of sawlogs may be transported to different sister factories.

Problem rows defined with Eq. (8) are interpreted using extended schedules as follows:

$$h_t = \sum_{k=1}^q b_{tk} z_k + \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j^+} \left(\sum_{k=1}^p (\alpha_{ijk} + \lambda_{ijkf(j^+)} + \gamma_{ijkf(j^+)g(j^+)}) x_k^{ij} \right) w_{ij^+} \quad (15)$$

Evidently, we have the constraint that extended schedules based on schedule j use the same proportion of the stand as schedule

$$w_{ij} = \sum_{j^+} w_{ij^+} \quad (16).$$

Consequently, as proportions w_{ij} add up to one in each stand, so do proportions w_{ij^+} :

$$\sum_{j^+} w_{ij^+} = 1 \quad (17)$$

I claim that problems with rows (8) and area constraints (11)- (13) can be solved solving the problem with rows (15) and area constraints (17) using exactly the same GUB technique used to solve problems without factories. In the suggested algorithm, an extended schedule tells that all x_k^{ij} is assigned to just one factory f_k^{j+} and that the same share w_{ij+} of different x_k^{ij} variables are assigned to their associated factories. But in practice different shares of different x_k^{ij} are associated to factories. So, it is not self-evident that extended schedules can do their job.

Any solution (either current or optimal) for a problem defined in Eq. (8) gives values w_{ij} , w_{ijkf} and w_{ijkfg} which satisfy the area constraints (11)- (13). The solution can be reproduced with extended schedule weights w_{ij+} if the extended schedule weights w_{ij+} are constructed with the following algorithm for each stand i and schedule j for which $w_{ij} > 0$.

If there are no linked g factories:

1. Start next extended schedule j^+ selecting such variable k^* and factory f^* that w_{ijkf} has the smallest nonzero value. Set $w_{ij+} = w_{ijk^*f^*}$. The extended schedule will have $f_{k^*}^{j+} = f^*$. Factory f^* for variable k^* is not used in later extended schedules.
2. For each $k \neq k^*$ select such factory to the extended schedule under construction that w_{ijkf} is nonzero. Point 1 implies that $w_{ijkf} \geq w_{ij+}$.
3. Set $w_{ijkf} = w_{ijkf} - w_{ij+}$ for the (k, f) pairs entering the extended schedule, including (k^*, f^*) obtained in 1. Set $w_{ij} = w_{ij} - w_{ij+}$.
4. If $w_{ij} > 0$ go to step 1. When $w_{ij} = 0$, all w_{ijkf} variables are also zero.

Updating of w_{ij} is needed only for following how w_{ij} is distributed to the extended schedules,

Termination can be checked also by checking whether all w_{ijkf} variables are zero. When checking condition $w_{ij} > 0$, rounding errors need to be considered.

If there are linked g factories, the algorithm is:

1. Start next extended schedule j^+ selecting such variable k^* and factory f^* and linked factory g^* that w_{ijkfg} has the smallest nonzero value. Set $w_{ij+} = w_{ijk^*f^*g^*}$. The extended schedule will have $g_{k^*}^{j+} = g^*$, $f_{k^*}^{j+} = f^*$. Factory g^* is not linked to f^* for variable k^* in later extended schedules.
2. For other $k \neq k^*$ select such factories f and linked factories g that w_{ijkf} and w_{ijkfg} are nonzero. Evidently $w_{ijkf} \geq w_{ij+}$ and $w_{ijkfg} \geq w_{ij+}$.
3. Set $w_{ijkf} = w_{ijkf} - w_{ij+}$, $w_{ijkfg} = w_{ijkfg} - w_{ij+}$ for all selected (k, f, g) triples, including (k^*, f^*, g^*) . Set $w_{ij} = w_{ij} - w_{ij+}$.
4. If $w_{ij} > 0$ go to step 1. When $w_{ij} = 0$, all w_{ijkf} and w_{ijkfg} variables are also zero.

Appendix shows a Jlp22 script which demonstrates the algorithm when linked factories are present.

The script and version of Jlp22 running this script are found at

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18096746>.

The following points need to be emphasized:

- The above algorithm or the Jlp22 script in the Appendix are not needed in practice. The only purpose is to show that with extended schedules, the same solution can be obtained as with w_{ij} , w_{ijkf} and w_{ijkfg} variables which define uniquely any solution satisfying the area constraints (11)-(13).
- In the artificial example in the Appendix there are 16 extended schedules corresponding to just one ordinary schedule. In the LP problems considered and solved using the GUB technique there are as many basic variables as there are constraint rows, not counting the area constraints. Some of basic variables may be z variables, or slack or surplus variables describing that neither the lower limit L_t or the upper limit U_t is binding. In typical problems there may be only tens or hundreds of constraints and thousands or tens of thousands of stands. Thus, in most stands the extended key schedule is the only extended schedule in the solution having nonzero w_{ij+} . In split stands there is typically only one extended schedule having nonzero w_{ij+} .

- There are several ways to reproduce a (w_{ij}, w_{ijkf}) or $(w_{ij}, w_{ijkf}, w_{ijkfg})$ solutions with extended schedules by making different choices in step 2 in both algorithms above.

Even if all $(w_{ij}, w_{ijkf}, w_{ijkfg})$ solutions can be presented in terms of extended schedules, we must look whether the extended schedule area constraint $\sum_{j^+} w_{ij^+} = 1$ is sufficient to guarantee that area constraint (11) and (12) are satisfied. Because in each extended schedule, the same share of area, w_{ij^+} is assigned to different factories, these area constraints are automatically satisfied.

3.3 Solving factory problems with extended schedules

The GUB technique can be used to take care area constraints $\sum_{j^+} w_{ij^+} = 1$ exactly in the same way as in problems without factories replacing α_{ik} in (5) with $\alpha_{ijk} + \lambda_{ijkf(j^+)} + \gamma_{ijkf(j^+)g(j^+)}$ in Eq. (15).

The algorithm of Lappi and Lempinen (2014) used in addition to key schedules also key factories for each stand i and x_k variable to get rid of constraints telling that all x_k in stand is transported to factories. Using extended schedules, we do not need any key factories, just key (extended) schedules. It is of course possible to use name 'key factory' for factories in a key extended schedule

Using the GUB technique in problems without factories, the value a schedule j in stand i is computed using

$$u_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^p \alpha_{0ijk} x_k^{ij} - \sum_{t=1}^T v_t \sum_{k=1}^p (\alpha_{ijk} x_k^{ij}) \quad (18)$$

where v_t is the price of constraint t telling how much the objective needs to pay to satisfy the constraint. Prices v_t are standard variables in LP computations. If u_{ij} is greater than the price of the key schedule, which is equal to the price of any basic schedule, the objective can increase if schedule j , i.e., w_{ij} enters the basis (see p. 112 in Lappi 1992, or Eq. (21) in Lappi and Lempinen 2014). The objective will not increase if the entering w_{ij} will be degenerate basic variable with value zero, but the

prices v_t will change. Any LP algorithm used in practice needs to consider the possibility of cycling.

Due to the GUB technique, the column entering the basis matrix does not consist of values $\alpha_{ijk}x_k^{ij}$ but of differences $\alpha_{ijk}x_k^{ij} - \alpha_{iiJ(i)k}x_k^{iJ(i)}$ where $J(i)$ is the current key schedule. Note that a z_k variable can enter the solution if $b_{0k} - \sum_t v_t b_{tk} > 0$. The entering column consists of values b_{tk} .

The power, in addition to getting rid of the original area constraints (11)-(13), of the suggested algorithm comes from an analysis of how the utility of a schedule in Eq. (18) is computed for extended schedules:

$$u_{ij^*} = \sum_{k=1}^p (u_{ijk} + u_{ijkf} + u_{ijkfg}) x_k^{ij} \quad (19)$$

where

$$u_{ijk} = \alpha_{0ijk} - \sum_{t=1}^T v_t \alpha_{tijk} \quad (20)$$

$$u_{ijkf} = \lambda_{0ijkf} - \sum_{t=1}^T v_t \lambda_{tijkf} \quad (21)$$

$$u_{ijkfg} = \gamma_{0ijkfg} - \sum_{t=1}^T v_t \gamma_{tijkfg} \quad (22)$$

If the utility of an extended schedule is greater than the utility of the key extended schedule, the extended schedule can enter the basis. Eqs. (19) - (22) can be utilized as follows.

Assume first that λ_{ijkf} and γ_{ijkfg} do not depend on schedule j . Then we can select the entering extended schedule in each stand i as follows:

Jlp22 algorithm when coefficients do not depend on schedule j

1. For each x_k and f to which x_k can be assigned, the best second level factory g is the factory producing maximum of u_{ijkfg} shown in (22).
2. For each x_k the best first level factory f is selected using $u_{ijkf} + u_{ijkfg}$ where u_{ijkfg} is obtained in step 1.
3. Thereafter we can select the optimal j which produces maximal value for Eq. (19).

The reason why f and g in Eqs. (19)-(22) are not written in form $f(j^+)$ and $g(j^+)$ is that these formulas are used to construct the extended schedule j^+ so j^+ cannot be an argument before it is constructed. Construction of the entering extended schedule resembles the logic of dynamic programming.

If both λ_{ijkf} and γ_{ijkfg} depend on j , then the two first steps of above algorithm needs to be applied for each schedule separately, and then compute the value of each extended schedule obtained separately. It is left as an exercise for the reader to plan the computations if either λ_{ijkf} or γ_{ijkfg} depends on j .

It is straightforward to allow sister factories to the second level factories g . Let d denote a sister for g , e.g. power plant to which bark of sawlogs is transported from a sawmill f . These sisters can be treated by adding into Eq. (8) a term using weights w_{ijkfd} and adding into the utility Eq. (19) a term u_{ijkfd} defined similarly as u_{ijkfg} is defined in Eq. (22). Note that all linked factories are specific for each x_k variable. Sister factories are needed when the same x_k variable is divided into parts, e.g. Scots pine sawlog in period 3 is divided into chips and bark.

The extended schedules give the possibility to optimize in the next step of the algorithm simultaneously the schedule j and assignments of all x_k variables. The formulation of Lappi and Lempinen (2014) assumed that all x_k coming from different schedules in stand i is first put together and then distributed to factories. Formula and computations were manageable but complicated. The

inefficient algorithm of Lappi and Lempinen (2014) iterates between changing basic schedules. i.e., entering w_{ij} variables and changing transportations x_k variables one variable at time.

Selection of the factories using (19) - (22) is the same as used in DTRAN. The prices used are based on the matrix theory of linear programming as they are heuristic approximations in DTRAN.

3.4 Implementation of the factory algorithm in Jlp22

I have not yet implemented the whole factory optimization into Jlp22. I decided to write this report before the final implementation, hoping that:

- Writing the report will clarify and organize the method which was in an intuitive and vague form in my mind. This succeeded well.
- The report would encourage someone somewhere to cooperate in the implementation or take care of the implementation.

The linear programming part of the implementation is a straightforward extension of the current GUB algorithm of Jlp22. It is more demanding to:

- Define the problem definition syntax easy for the users. The current development version is otherwise quite reasonable, but I have not yet implemented the possibility to use sister factories to the second level factories g .
- Allow users to define easy to use data structures for defining location (stand) dependent coefficients λ_{ijkf} and γ_{ijkfg} . It must be possible to use both simple coordinate-based distances and more accurate transportation costs computed using existing road and lake networks.
- Allow the user to balance between speed and memory requirements. If there is no shortage of memory, all λ_{ijkf} and γ_{ijkfg} coefficients can be computed in advance. Working with large data sets, even 64 bit memory may be too small without paying attention to the memory. Jlp22 is using 64 bit integers to refer matrix elements as 32 bit integers holding integers up to 2147 million proved to be too small in large forestry problems even without factories.

- Allow using only neighboring factories (already implemented). This is similar to the property of existing algorithm to consider only schedules which are in the active set defined using Eq (18) to select a subset of good schedules.

Jlp22 has a second level programming called input programming which operates on text lines and can generate a large number of long text lines with few short lines. In the input programming loops like ;do(i,1,20), the value of index variable can be put into different parts of names of other variables within the loop. This way a user can, with very few input lines produce a large number of code lines having understandable variable names. This is useful in ordinary problems without factories when loops are made over periods. In factory problems nested loops can be made over periods, sawmills, pulp mills and power plants. Definition of one problem row may utilize several nested input programming loops.

In old times, linear programming applications used three separate programs: matrix generator, solver and report writer. Jlp22 has data manipulation, text line manipulation and graphics capabilities to do everything in an integrated programming environment.

4 Discussion

4.1 Methodological comments

LP algorithms for special cases have been developed so long that it is not easy to develop theoretically something new. The history of JLP repeats here, I reinvented what old masters invented long time ago. When I had temporary confusion when trying to demonstrate that the extended schedules work as I imagined, I looked what Hillier and Lieberman (1974) wrote in their classic book. It seems to me that the decomposition method presented there is the method presented above. The decomposition method analyzes problems having general constraint rows using all decision variables and subproblem constraint rows using different subsets of variables. The analysis reformulates problems as weighted sums of extreme points where weights add up to one in each subproblem. Extreme points of a subproblem are the corner points of the convex set where the constraints of the subproblem are satisfied. My extended schedules are the extreme points satisfying area constraints (11) - (13). Hillier and Lieberman did not suggest at this point to use GUB technique to deal with the constraints telling that subproblem weights add up to one in each subproblem, but this continuation is evident, as well as inclusion of z variables. My extended schedules have specific structure with second level factories and their sister factories, as described above. Such nested problems were studied already by Glassey

(1973), and the review of Wen and Hsu (1991) deal with similar things. However, after recovering from my confusion, it was easier for me to continue with my own derivations than try to put everything into the form used in previous studies. Perhaps my contribution here is to show explicitly what are the extreme points in LP problems described by rows (8). My algorithm may be useful in practice similarly as the GUB algorithms in JLP, J and Jlp22 have been even without theoretical merits.

Gunn (2009) analyzed strategic aspects of forest management and supply chain collecting first timber from a region into one central point and then distributed it to factories. It may sound strange that the transportation of timber to factories is done here separately each schedule j in a given stand i instead of collecting each timber type together in the stand and then consider the distribution to different factories as done in Lappi and Lempinen (2014). Even more strange is to consider transportation chips from sawmills to pulp mills (or power plants) already at schedule level. Sawmills do not keep track of which stand chips come, so why not put all chips also computationally into one variable which is then distributed further? Building computationally intermediate storages would require new constraints and new decision variables. I claim that the above procedure is more efficient, similarly as it is more efficient to send e-mail to someone in another city directly instead of sending e-mails first to e-mail post office which then delivers it to the recipient. It is possible that such interface which allows description of chip transportation in terms of distributing a chip pile into second level factories is convenient. But the software developer needs to translate this problem description into the above more efficient description.

It would be interesting to develop the algorithm for stochastic optimization similarly as DTRAN is applied in De Pellegrin (2022).

Even if LP has been utilized for long time in forestry, e.g. as presented in Dykstra (1984), I think that not all of its possibilities have been utilized. One obstacle is that interfaces available in commercial software do not allow easy problem definitions. I indicated in (Lappi 2024) how linear programming could provide prices which could be used in the bucking algorithm of a harvester to obtain required amounts of different sawn product dimensions. I claimed that popular distribution bucking aiming at given distribution of sawlog dimensions is not rational. I have already developed into Jlp22 functions which allow easy definition of LP problems which produce needed sawing blade settings when a sawlog storage of different sawlog dimensions is available and amounts of sold sawn wood dimensions are given.

There are many kinds of optimization problems in forestry, dealing with transportation costs which cannot be analyzed within the presented formulation (see Rönqvist 2003 for a review). Planning problems at the tactical or operative level need more specific problem formulations and solution methods.

4.2 Possible developments of the linear programming algorithm

There are several ways to fine tune the above problem description without the need to change the software. For instance, it is simple to include import and export of the timber in the algorithm. Border points where timber enters a country can be defined as theoretical stands. Border points where timber leaves a country can be defined as factories.

The current implementation of the LP algorithm and common practice assumes that α_{ik} in (5) does not depend on i and j . If the factory optimization problems make people to consider the possibility that α_{ik} depends on i and j as expressed in (8), this may lead to new ideas. One application of making λ_{ijkf} to depend on schedule j is that the costs of applying treatments are e.g. in MELA computations now put into a different x_k variable. The formulation with λ_{ijkf} allows to combine treatment costs, transportation costs and utilities into one coefficient.

The relations between prices and utilities depend whether a problem is formulated from the perspective of the owners of factory f , linked factory g , or the owners of stands, or from the viewpoint of the national economy. Formulating several optimization problems from different perspectives with the same forest data gives possibilities to study market equilibrium questions or what effect it has on the national economy that current timber trade in Finland does not fulfill any requirements of market economy as shown in Lappi (2024).

There are several ways to develop the current LP algorithm of Jlp22.

- Goal programming problems need now be described defining slack and surplus variables as z variables. Jlp22 algorithm treats now inequality constraints using residuals of Fletcher subroutines, which can be positive or negative and which do the same thing as slack and

surplus variables in traditional formulations. Residuals are now hidden from the users. It would be quite easy to allow users to access these variables directly in the problem definition. Jlp22 uses residuals in the objective already now when finding a feasible solution.

- Jlp22 can compute derivatives of functions using the derivation rules. It would be quite easy to allow nonlinear functions of x variables in the objective function using first order Taylor series as temporary objective. In forestry problems x variables change in small steps when the basis matrix is updated in a stand. This makes implementation of nonlinear functions easier than in general nonlinear problems without a natural step size.
- The ordinary and generalized upper bound techniques used in Jlp22 require the right-hand sides of constraints are continuously changed. Thus, it would be straightforward to develop the updating subroutines so that piecewise linear functions can be used also in constraints.

4.3 Requirements for the simulator

Taking full advantage of factory optimization problems defined above puts requirement to the simulator which generates the x_k^{ij} values. A simulator should also give such information of stands and schedules not expressed in x_k variables that a user can give proper values for coefficients λ_{ijkf} and γ_{ijkfg} . The current MELA simulator does not produce proper data for studying bucking and timber trade questions. For instance, MELA just computes sawlog volumes but does not give information of diameter distribution. I claimed in Lappi (2024) that the current dominant assortment pricing is harmful to Finnish forestry also because it has led researchers to concentrate on poorly defined sawlog volumes which buyers can almost freely determine after the deal instead of on sawn timber and chip volumes and their values.

Developers of MELA and I have had since 1991 conflicting views about optimal division of labor between JLP and MELA. I tried to suggest that the simulator should just compute the development of forest variables under different treatments, and economic variables would be computed using the transformation possibilities of JLP. The data management possibilities provided with Jlp22 are now far better than are in JLP, and computations with Jlp22 scripts are very fast. Another disagreement was that I like the idea of control using a script-based programming language. MELA is based on control with parameters. Evidently the current simulator developments will put the dominant Finnish national simulator on a higher level.

4.4 Final comments

Both computers and software products are developing now so fast due to artificial intelligence that it is impossible to predict whether the factory algorithm as presented here will be useful. Even if I could implement the algorithm in Jlp22 soon, as I hope, I'm not optimistic of the long-term perspectives of the Jlp22 software. No-one has been interested in the development of the open Jlp22 since 2022 even if the current version contains substantially cleaner code than the version of J Luke insisted on publishing without my involvement. Especially, the LP code of J was very dirty. JLP code from 1992 is still used in MELA computations. It is not likely that Jlp22 will survive that long without active development.

I hope that this paper helps to formulate proper factory optimization problems and gives theoretical insight to forestry planning problems including factories and shows an example how tailored LP algorithms can be developed for special problem types.

Supplementary files

Available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18096746> script file algo.txt and program Jlp22.exe which can execute the script shown in the Appendix.

Declarations

Jlp22 software is available as open source software at github.com/juhalappi/Jlp22. Jlp22 is distributed under the terms of the GNU Affero General Public License.

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APPENDIX

Algorithm demonstrating the algorithm which shows that extended schedules can generate all solutions in the factory optimization when there are both first level factories f and second level

second level g factories. The algorithm ‘eats’ original weights w_{ij} , w_{ijkf} and w_{ijkfg} and distributes these into the weights w_{ij+} of the extended schedules. The software and script for using the algorithm is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18096746>. The whole Jlp package including the manual, precompiler for easy access to data structure, the program for writing Latex code for the manual from comments embedded in source files and writing a script file for all examples in the manual is available at github.com/juhalappi/Jlp22

```

! A Jlp22 script for demonstrating that extended schedules can produce
! any solution where timber is transported into factories and
! from first level factories to second level factories.
! To run the script:
! Put Jlp22.exe and libgcc_s_seh-1.dll libgfortran-5.dll
! libquadmath-0.dll libwinpthread-1.dll into any folder
! start Command Prompt in the same folder
! Type at command prompt jlp22 algo.txt
! at sit> prompt type end or any Jlp22 commands

wij=0.7 ! Weigt for a schedule.
! There are 3 xk variables and for each 3 factories.
! Rows are for xl variables and columns for factories.
! Semicolon at the end indicates that the result is printed.
wijmat=matrix(3,3,in->);
0.2 ,0.4,0.1
0.3,0.2,0.2
0.15,0.25,0.3
/
! Check that rows sum up to wij
!
rowsums=sum(wijmat,row->);

! Secondary factories. Three first columns tell wijkfg when the first factory is
1
!Thus they need to sum up to the first element in row k in wijmat.
!
wijmat2=matrix(3,9,in->)
0.05,0.1,0.05,0.1,0.2,0.1,0.02,0.03,0.05 !
0.1,0.05,0.15,0.1,0.05,0.05,0.05,0.05,0.1
0.05,0.06,0.04,0.1,0.1,0.05,0.1,0.15,0.05
/

Wij1=sum(wijmat2(All,1,-3),row->); !this should be equal to first column in
wijmat
Wij2=sum(wijmat2(All,4,-6),row->);
Wij3=sum(wijmat2(All,7,-9),row->);

rowsums2=Wij1+Wij2+Wij3;

F=3 !nuber of factories
F2=3 !number of second level factories
K=3 !Number of xk variable
fext_=matrix(1000,F) ! 3 first factories of extended schedules

```

```

fext2_=matrix(1000,F2) ! 3 second level factories
wijplus_=matrix(1000) ! weights of extended schedules
wijrest_=matrix(1000) ! the amount of weight wij still to be put into extended
schedules
wrest_=matrix(1000) !remaining weight of first factories
wrest2_=matrix(1000) !remeaning weights of second level factories

tr=trans() !define a tranformation set
do(jp,1,1000) !jp =number of extended schedule, maximum 1000
    !jp,0,wijmat,wijmat2;
    mini=1 !minimum value
    do(k,1,K)
    do(f,1,F)
        do(f2,1,F2)
            if(wijmat2(k,(f-1)*F2+f2).gt.0.0001.and.wijmat2(k,(f-
1)*F2+f2).lt.mini)then
                mini=wijmat2(k,(f-1)*F2+f2)
                kmin=k
                fmin=f
                fmin2=f2
            endif
        enddo !f2
    enddo !f
enddo !k

! jp,kmin,fmin,fmin2,mini;
if(mini.eq.1)then
    !all done
    jp1=jp-1
    fext=fext_(1,-jp1,All) !first level factories
    fext2=fext2_(1,-jp1,All)
    wijplus=wijplus_(1,-jp1)
    wrest=wrest_(1,-jp1)
    wrest2=wrest2_(1,-jp1)
    wijrest=wijrest_(1,-jp1)
    return
endif

wijplus_(jp)=mini
fext_(jp,kmin)=fmin
fext2_(jp,kmin)=fmin2
wijmat(kmin,fmin)=wijmat(kmin,fmin)-mini
wijmat2(kmin,(fmin-1)*F2+fmin2)=wijmat2(kmin,(fmin-1)*F2+fmin2)-mini
wij=wij-mini
wijrest_(jp)=wij

do(k,1,K)
    if(k.ne.kmin)then
        do(f,1,3)
            do(f2,1,3)
                if(wijmat2(k,(f-1)*F2+f2).gt.0.0001)then
                    wijmat2(k,(f-1)*F2+f2)=wijmat2(k,(f-1)*F2+f2)-mini
                    wijmat(k,f)=wijmat(k,f)-mini
                    fext_(jp,k)=f
                    fext2_(jp,k)=f2
                goto(done)
            endif
        enddo
    endif
enddo

```

```

        enddo          !f2
    enddo !f
        done:
    endif !k.ne.kmin
    enddo !k
    wrest_(jp)=sum(wijmat,any->) !remaining sum of wijmat
        wrest2_(jp)=sum(wijmat2,any->) !remaing sum of wijmat2
    !jp,mini,wijmat,wijmat2; ! uncomment to print
    enddo !jp
/

call(tr)

totm=matrix(1,6 ,values->(fext,fext2,wijplus,wijrest,wrest,wrest2),matrix->)

write($,'(6f4.0,5f7.3)',totm)
**  fact          fact2  wijplus  wijrest, remainingg wijmat, remaining wijmat2

;return

```